

Ocular Manifestations in Cutaneous Autoimmune Connective Tissue Diseases**G. Madhavi Latha¹, Esam Sathya Narayana Murthy², Ramadevi³, Y. Anuhaya⁴**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Sidhartha Medical College, Dr. N.T.R. University of Health Sciences, Vijayawada, AP, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Sidhartha Medical College, Dr. N.T.R University of Health Sciences, Vijayawada, AP, India³Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Sidhartha Medical College, Dr. N.T.R University of Health Sciences, Vijayawada, AP, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Sidhartha Medical College, Dr. N.T.R University of Health Sciences, AP, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr Esam Sathya Narayana Murthy

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Purpose:** To study the prevalence of ophthalmic manifestations in cutaneous autoimmune connective tissue diseases, to monitor the progression of ocular manifestations.**Methods:** Retrospective, non-comparative, observational cohort study in tertiary care hospital, from July 2022 to December 2022, in 40 adult patients, with cutaneous autoimmune connective tissue disease. The demographic data, history, ophthalmic examination including visual acuity, slit lamp examination, dry eye tests, and fundus examination visual field test were recorded.**Results:** Majority of patients were in the age group 31-40 years (55%). The prevalence of ocular manifestations in cutaneous autoimmune connective tissue diseases was 72.5%. Wherein 79.3 % patients had anterior segment involvement and 20.7% patients had posterior segment involvement. Rheumatoid arthritis being the most common disease with ocular manifestations 57.5%.**Conclusions:** In cutaneous autoimmune connective tissue diseases, prevalence of ocular manifestations in our study was 72.5%. Females were more commonly and aggressively affected. It is essential to screen patients for ocular manifestations.**Keywords:** Ocular manifestations, Dry eye, anterior and posterior uveitis, Cystoid macular edema, connective tissue diseases, rheumatoid arthritis, SLE, Sarcoidosis, Sjogren syndrome.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Cutaneous Connective tissue diseases (CTDs) are a group of clinical disorders that have an underlying autoimmune pathogenesis. These include a diverse set of diseases such as Sarcoidosis, rheumatoid arthritis, and Behcet's disease, along with more common entities like Sjogren's syndrome, dermatomyositis, scleroderma, and lupus erythematosus.

The ocular involvement correlate with the disease severity and duration. Often eyes may be the first presenting feature of CTDs. Patients with known CTDs should have periodic ophthalmic examination to monitor for ocular involvement as well as to diagnose any treatment related complications.

Ocular involvement include the ocular adnexa (lids, lashes, and orbit), tear film, sclera, cornea, the uveal tract, lens, vitreous cavity or the retina.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

1. To study ocular manifestations in patients with cutaneous autoimmune connective tissue disorders
2. To study the prevalence of ophthalmic manifestations in known cases of cutaneous connective tissue diseases.
3. To analyse the involvement of anterior and posterior segment of the eye in these diseases.
4. To monitor the progression of the ocular manifestations

Materials and Methodology

It is Retrospective, non-comparative, observational cohort study in tertiary care hospital, from July 2022 to December 2022. Sample size was 40 patients (80eyes).

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All patients diagnosed with cutaneous connective tissue diseases by Dermatology department, based on antibody titers and clinical criteria for diagnosis of connective tissue diseases.
2. Patients with ocular symptoms who presented to ophthalmology OPD, suspicious connective tissue disease based on history and clinical examination, whose diagnosis was confirmed by dermatology department.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Ocular symptoms due to some other cause, pre-existing ocular disease, and comorbid illness like diabetes.

Data Collection: Demographic data of patients were documented. Ocular symptoms like blurring

of vision, redness, pain and photophobia, foreign body sensation were noted.

Ophthalmic examination included visual acuity, slit lamp examination, dry eye tests [Schirmer's test, Tear Film Break Up time (TBUT)], Rose Bengal staining, dilated fundus examination (Fundus fluorescein angiography wherever indicated). Visual Acuity was examined using Snellen's chart. Undilated slit lamp examination was done to look for keratoconjunctivitis sicca (KCS), episcleritis, scleritis, anterior uveitis and complicated cataract. Intraocular pressure was measured on applanation tonometry. Tests for Dry eye were performed: Schirmer's test, Tear film break up time (TBUT). TBUT <10 seconds was considered abnormal.

Ocular surface staining with Rose Bengal stain was done. Positive corneal and conjunctival staining was considered abnormal.

Dry eye was graded as follows and accordingly treated:

Grade	Schimer's test value (mm)	Severity
0	>10	No dry eye
1	6-10	Mild
2	3-5	Moderate
3	<3	Severe

In relevant cases with posterior segment involvement, Fundus Fluorescein Angiography was performed in patients with normal basic renal function tests.

Patients were treated with the following for specific conditions: Dry eye was treated with Carboxy-methyl cellulose(CMC) eye drops (0.5%- in mild to moderate dry eye 6-8 times in a day and 1% in severe dry eye two hourly). Temporary punctal plugs were given in both puncta of one eye in a case of severe dry eye in a case of Sjogren's syndrome. After consent, the silicon plugs were inserted in both the upper and lower puncta of right eye under slit lamp with a Mac Pherson forceps followed by tapering dose of low potency steroid, Loteprednol (0.5%) eye drops.

Filamentary keratitis was treated by N acetyl cysteine (10%) eye drops were added to CMC eye drops 6 times in a day along with Eyedrops Homatropine (2%). Acute anterior uveitis was treated with four week course of Eye drops Prednisolone (1%) or Loteprednol (0.5%) six times in a day based on severity of inflammation along with Eyedrops

Homatropine (2%). Ptosis in case of dermatomyositis was treated initially with oral glucocorticoids 0.5mg/kg body weight along with weekly methotrexate of 22.5 mg in three divided doses.

No surgical treatment was indicated for any complications.

For posterior uveitis and intermediate uveitis: posterior subtenon injection triamcinolone acetonide (0.5 cc = 20mg) was given along with systemic steroids (Tablet Prednisolone 1mg/kg tapered over six weeks.)

Cystoid macular edema was treated with a single injection of preservative free intravitreal Triamcinolone acetonide (0.1 ml = 4 mg). At follow up visits, patient's evaluation with respect to best corrected visual acuity, the dry eye tests, slit lamp examination and fundus imaging wherever relevant was done. Patient's symptomatic improvement was asked. Symptomatic patients were evaluated on day three, day seven and then weekly for a month and then every three months and as required. Asymptomatic patients were evaluated at third and sixth months.

Table 1: Age-wise distribution of patients

Sr. No.	Age distribution(Years)	No. of Patients	Percentage of patients
1	21-30	6	15%
2	31-40	22	55%
3	41-50	9	22.5%
4	51-60	3	7.5%
	Total	40	100%

Table 2: Sex-wise distribution of patients

Sr. No	Sex	No. of patients	Percentage of patients (%)
1	Male	6	15%
2	Female	34	85%
	Total	40	100%

Table 3: Prevalence of ocular manifestations in Connective tissue diseases

Sr. No	Disease	No. of patients with no ocular Manifestations	No. of patients with ocular manifestations			Total no. of patients with the disease	% of affected patients
			(Males)	females)	Total		
1	RA	9	3	11	14	23	61%
2	Scleroderma	0	0	1	1	1	100%
3	Sarcoidosis	0	0	3	3	3	100%
4	Sjogrens Syndrome	0	0	2	2	2	2%
5	SLE	2	1	6	7	9	78%
6	Behcet's Disease	0	0	1	1	1	100%
7	Dermatomyositis	0	0	1	1	1	100%
	Total	11	4	25	29	40	72.5%
		Total patients with ocular manifestations=					

Table 4: Prevalence of anterior segment involvement in Connective tissue diseases

Sr. No	Disease	No. of patients with Anterior segment manifestations			No. of patients with ocular manifestations in the disease	% of patients with anterior segment manifestations
		Males	Females	Total		
1	RA	2	12	14	14	100%
2	Scleroderma	0	1	1	1	100%
3	Sarcoidosis	0	1	1	3	33%
4	Sjogren's Syndrome	0	2	2	2	100%
5	SLE	1	2	3	7	42.8%
6	Behcet's Disease	0	1	1	1	100%
7.	Dermatomyositis	0	1	1	1	100%
	Total	3	20	23	29	79.3%

Table 5: Different types of anterior segment manifestations noted in the study.

Manifestation	No. of patients (%)
Dry eye	8
Filamentary keratitis	1
Episcleritis	3
Scleritis	4
Anterior uveitis	7
Complicated cataract	1
Ptosis	1

Table 6: Prevalence of posterior segment manifestations in connective tissue diseases

Sr. No	Disease	No. of patients with posterior segment manifestations			No. of patients with ocular manifestations in the disease	% of patients with posterior segment manifestations
		Males	Females	Total		
1	RA	0	0	0	14	0
2	Scleroderma	0	0	0	1	0
3	Sarcoidosis	0	2	2	3	66.66%
4	Sjogren's Syndrome	0	0	0	2	0
5	SLE	1	2	3	7	57%
6	Behcet's Disease	0	1	1	1	0
7	Dermatomyositis	0	0	0	1	0
	Total	1	5	6	29	20.7%

Table 7: Different types of posterior segment manifestations

Type of Manifestation	No. of patients
Vasculitis/Posterior uveitis	3
CME	3
Central serous chorioretinopathy	1

Table 8: Best corrected Visual acuity in the study population at the initial presentation

Visual acuity	No. of eyes (%)
6/18-6/6	72
6/60 -6/24	25
1/60-5/60	2
PL+, projection of rays present, HM, CF	1

Table 9: Progression of ocular manifestations over the study period

Follow up over	3 months	6 months
Improved	12	14
Status quo	26	22
Worsened	2	1

Table 10: Patients who lost to follow up

Months of follow up	Total
No. of patients lost to follow up	3

Discussion

The prevalence of ocular involvement in systemic sarcoidosis ranges from 12%-76% with ocular involvement being the presenting symptom in 30-40%. The most common types of ocular involvement are uveitis and conjunctival nodule.

Ocular involvement in dermatomyositis is a rare finding that usually manifests weakness of the extraocular muscle or retinopathy. The heliotrope eyelid eruption is considered as a hallmark of DM. Patients can present with blurry vision and/or diplopia, ptosis, conjunctival edema, nystagmus, extraocular muscle imbalance, iritis, cotton wool spots, optic atrophy, and conjunctival pseudo polyposis.

In our study, of the 40 patients with cutaneous connective tissue diseases 57.5% (23 patients) had Rheumatoid arthritis, 22.5% (9 patients) had Systemic Lupus Erythematosus, 7.5% (3 patients) were of Sarcoidosis, 5% (2 patients) Sjogren's Syndrome, 2.5% (1 patient) Scleroderma, 2.5% (1 patient) Behcet's, 2.5% (1 patient), Dermatomyositis.

The patients were maximum in the age group of 31-40 years (55%) followed by age group of 41-50 years (22.5%), followed by age group of 21-30 (15%). Only 7.5% (3 patients) were in the age group of 51 years and above. The mean age of the cohort in the study was 37 years. Middle age population are predominantly affected with connective tissue diseases in our study. Females were more affected (85%) than males in all diseases in our study. 72.5% of the affected patients had anterior segment manifestations in our study.

In cases of RA, all 14 patients (i.e. 61% of RA pa-

tients) had anterior segment manifestations. Dry eye was most common i.e. in five patients followed by filamentary keratitis in three patients and three patients presented with anterior uveitis. In the present study, only one case of Scleroderma was identified. Patient had severe dry eye and chronic granulomatous uveitis. According to a study by Waszczykowska et al incidence of keratoconjunctivitis sicca in scleroderma was 22%. [5]

In the present study, Sarcoidosis was present in 7.5% cases (three patients). All three patients had anterior uveitis and two patients had posterior uveitis. [6] Both patients of Sjogren's syndrome had severe dry eye. Sjogren's syndrome is characterized by dry eye and dry mouth due to involvement of lacrimal and salivary glands. Keratoconjunctivitis sicca (KCS) is the most common ocular manifestation.

In the present study, 43% of SLE patients had dry eye. In SLE, sicca syndrome 56 patients (15 - 30%), episcleritis, conjunctivitis, retinal vasculitis (5%) have been reported by Frith P. et al. [7] Thus the most common anterior segment manifestation in connective tissue disease was dry eye (8 patients) and filamentary keratitis mainly attributed to Rheumatoid arthritis followed by SLE and Sjogren's Syndrome. Of which 6 females and 2 males had dry eye, while 1 female had filamentary keratitis. Episcleritis was present in 2 females and 1 male. Scleritis was present in 3 females and 1 male, the severe form of scleromalacia being present in female. Anterior uveitis was equally distributed in both sexes. Anterior segment complications like complicated cataract, presented in female.

Posterior segment manifestations were found in 6 patients (20.7%) in the present study. Of which

posterior uveitis in the form of perivascular sheathing and cotton wool spots were present in two patients of Sarcoidosis, along with CME in one of them, one patient of Behcet's Disease and three patients of SLE. Two patient of SLE had only RE Cystoid macular edema confirmed on OCT. One patient of SLE presented with RE Central serous chorioretinopathy. One male patient of Sarcoidosis presented with only LE intermediate uveitis with no systemic features. He was then diagnosed as ocular sarcoidosis. Posterior segment manifestations were present more in females. Visual acuity in most patients was better than 6/18. 58 eyes had vision between 6/18-6/6. 20 eyes had vision between 6/60 to 6/24. One eye had vision between 1/60 to 5/60 due to anterior uveitis. One of the patients had long standing corneal opacity in one eye. Most of the elderly population had low visual acuity due to lenticular sclerosis. Only one eye had vision limited to perception of Light with accurate projection of rays. The visual acuity of the patients in the study was monitored. 3 patients were lost to follow up over six months. Of the 37 patients, maximum patients (22 patients) maintained the status quo as the presentation and few patients have improved (14 patients). One patient worsened which was attributable to long duration of the disease, severity of disease at presentation, Behcet's disease which shows fast progression, development of complicated cataract.

Conclusions

We studied 40 adults diagnosed as cutaneous autoimmune connective tissue disease referred form Dermatology OPD. Majority of patients were in the age group 31-40 years (55%). Female to male ratio was 5:1. Most common disease in the study was Rheumatoid arthritis which constituted 57.5% of the total study population. The prevalence of ocular manifestations was 72.5%. Anterior segment involvement is observed in 79.3% and posterior segment involvement is seen in 20.7% of study patients.

In patients with anterior segment involvement, most common presentation was Dry eye and its sequelae. Most patients had a visual acuity of better than 6/18. Only 2 eyes had visual acuity less than 1/60. Only one patient had worsened at the end of the study. Rest of them remained the same or had improved on treatment.

These ocular manifestations can result from the disease itself or treatments used to combat the primary autoimmune disease. The manifestations may be vision threatening if not attended to at an appropriate time. Hence it is necessary to screen patients for ocular manifestations with or without symptoms

to institute early management in these cases.

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